

METHODS OF TRAINING FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS TO USE INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON THE BASIS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14252781>

Abstract. *This article provides information on the forms of use of innovative pedagogical technologies on lessons by future primary school teachers based on independent learning.*

Keywords: *innovation, innovator, intellect, pedagogy, education, didactic games.*

Since the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has been elevated to the level of state policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and professions in conditions that meet world standards, grow up as physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities and talents, intellectual potential, and cultivate feelings of loyalty and selflessness to the Motherland in the hearts of our youth. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated April 20, 2017 - On measures to further develop the higher education system - is significant in that it is both a logical continuation of the work being carried out to reform the education system in our country and aimed at raising it to a new level. One of the most important aspects of the resolution is that it focuses on compliance with international standards in the training of highly qualified specialists, creating conditions at its level, and training personnel with modern knowledge and skills in accordance with their spirit and requirements. The early years of school after kindergarten play an important role in a child's life. Therefore, the period of primary education is the most responsible period in the educational process. At this time, along with the emergence of literacy, the child's worldview is formed, and the ability to think is developed.

During this period, each activity aimed at cultivating the child's mind has a great impact on the formation and development of the child's mind. Therefore, during this period, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to organizing the educational process in an interesting and effective way, to creating and developing motivation. Because this period is characterized by the child's transition from play activity to mental activity, that is, to educational activity. The use of various games is of great importance in the development of the child's educational activity. Children improve their knowledge through play and deeply assimilate it. From this point of view, the role of didactic games used in the educational process is invaluable. Didactic games increase the effectiveness of the educational process, develop students' activity in the educational process, and their motivation to study. The stages of independent learning are usually divided into the following main stages:

1. Preparatory stage: At this stage, the student identifies his interests and goals, collects the necessary materials and resources for studying.

2. Reading and learning stage: The student begins to master knowledge in the chosen topic or area. In this process, he studies books, articles, video lessons and other sources.

3. Practice stage: Applying the acquired knowledge in practice, experimenting and completing various tasks and projects to consolidate the mastered material.

4. Analysis and evaluation stage: The student analyzes his knowledge, evaluates the results and, if necessary, revises his approach.

5. Improvement stage: The student sets new goals and continues to study new materials to further deepen and develop his knowledge.

These stages may differ depending on the individual needs of each student, but in general, this is how the independent learning process develops.

Independent learning factors are important for a student to be successful in their self-directed learning process. The following factors help make independent learning effective:

1. Motivation: The learner's enthusiasm and interest in achieving their goals. Motivation is the main force behind independent learning.

2. Self-management: The learner must manage their time, resources, and energy effectively. This includes planning, goal setting, and self-control.

3. Learning strategies: Knowledge and application of various learning methods and strategies (e.g., memory techniques, study materials, etc.).

4. Access to resources: Free access to materials, resources, and tools (books, online courses, video lessons, etc.) necessary for learning.

5. Analytical skills: The ability to analyze and evaluate the acquired knowledge, apply the learned material in practice.

6. Self-assessment: The learner must analyze his/her achievements and shortcomings and take the necessary measures to improve the future learning process.

7. Social support: Support and advice provided by parents, friends, or mentors. Social connections can increase motivation in the process of independent learning.

8. Interests and abilities: The student's ability to identify his interests and abilities and choose a direction of study accordingly.

These factors play an important role in achieving success in the process of independent learning and can develop in accordance with the individual needs of each student.

Learning motivation also plays an important role in organizing the educational process based on pedagogical technologies. Didactic games greatly contribute to the effective progress of education in primary grades and the successful management of students' learning and cognitive activities, that is, theoretical knowledge is easily acquired through didactic games, and students' interest in learning increases. Didactic games can be a great impetus for the development of students' passion for knowledge not only in primary grades, but also in later stages of education. Such games are particularly effective in increasing the cognitive abilities of students with difficult learning difficulties. It should be noted that the lack of materials in this area is noticeable in the textbooks being created for primary grades.

Nowadays, great attention is paid to the organization of education based on pedagogical technologies. Pedagogical technology is the skill of choosing and developing the most convenient ways and methods to achieve the desired result for the implementation of educational forms, taking into account the abilities, possibilities and needs of students, and it really increases the productivity of the educational process, forms the independent thinking process of students, increases students' enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, forms the skills and qualifications for the solid assimilation of knowledge and its free use in practice. In pedagogical technology, it is important to determine the goal of the educational process, which should guarantee the planned results. Therefore,

teachers should pay special attention to clearly defining the goal. Each teacher must first clearly define the subject he teaches and the goal of each lesson.

It should be noted that if a clear project of the didactic process is developed based on the established goal, its implementation will be easier. It is good for primary school teachers to use various didactic games to organize each lesson. Because the school period is a rather difficult period in the life of 6-7-year-old children, and children face serious tests. The child enters a new life - school life. Now he is forced to feel that he is a member of a new team, to obey discipline, to adapt to a new regime. Despite the fact that the child is young, now he has many necessary tasks, such as studying at school, doing homework, and studying complex materials. It is important that the transition from play to school, to daily mandatory and continuous work, is a fundamental turning point in the child's life. Even for children who come from preschool institutions, this is not easy. And it is even more difficult for children who come from home to school. Especially, sitting in a 40-45 minute class, listening and completing assignments, and long mental work quickly tire a child. A child may become bored with school and studying. That is why teachers should strive to organize children's school life in an interesting way, create and develop motivation. Motivation does not arise by itself. It can be created through didactic games and independent work appropriate to the age and psychological characteristics of children.

Especially in the process of primary education, it is effective to attract students to the lesson as a result of conducting lessons in an interesting way using pedagogical technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Avliyoqulov N.X., Musaeva N. Pedagogik texnologiyalar. Toshkent-2008-yil
2. Avliyoqulov N.X. Zamonaviy o'qitish texnologiyalari – Toshkent, 2001
3. Adizov B.R. Boshlang'ich ta'limni ijodiy tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari.T., 2003-yil
4. Azizxo'jaeva N.N. Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar– Toshkent, 2002-yil
5. Хайдарова, Х. (2020). РАЗВИТИЕ ВИРТУАЛЬНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ РОДИТЕЛЕЙ КАК АКТУАЛЬНАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА. InterConf .